

District Development Council: an initiative for strengthening democracy in Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract :- Among the rising heat over Article 370 revocations in valley, the parliament of India in October 2020 amended the Jammu and Kashmir Panchayati Raj Act, 1989, to hold direct elections to District Development Council (DDC) with a stated goal of strengthening democracy at the gross root level. Almost after the fourteen months of revocation of special status of Jammu and Kashmir, the election was first political engagement which attracted the attention of the whole country. The paper attempts to examine the evolution of Panchayati Raj system in Jammu and Kashmir. The paper further analysed the structure of DDC and the objectives behind the creation of the Council.

Introduction :- Following the landmark constitutional amendments of 2019, the year 2020 began among uncertainty in valley. Most of the mainstream leaders were in detention. Though some political leaders were released in the first two months of the year, supposedly after signing a bond not to speak against the abrogation of Article 370. The outbreak of coronavirus pandemic hastened the release of many others including Farooq Abdullah and Omar Abdullah in March. However the Mehbooba Mufti head of the People's Democratic Party was released in October, just ahead of DDC elections. Anti-corruption agencies intensified probes against mainstream leaders during the year 2020. Under such circumstances the parliament of India in October 2020 amended the Jammu and Kashmir Panchayati Raj Act, 1989, to hold direct elections to District Development Council (DDC) with a stated goal of strengthening democracy at the gross root level. DDC elections were the first elections held in the Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir after the scraping of the erstwhile

state's semi-autonomous status and its division into two separate UTs: J&K and Ladakh by the Narendra Modi government. But the successful conduct of the DDC elections was highlight of 2020.

Historical Background of Panchayati Raj System in Jammu and Kashmir

:- During the British period, while as in the rest of the country the Panchayati Raj system passed through various phases, in the State of J&K it was only in 1935 when the first Village Panchayat Regulation Act No. 1 was promulgated by the then Maharaja Hari Singh. The preamble of the act, states "it is expedient to establish in Jammu and Kashmir state the village panchayats to assist in the administration of the civil and criminal justice and also to manage the sanitation and other common concerns of the village".

The act made provision that every village or a group of village had a Panchayat comprised of Panches numbering 5-7, elected by simply show of hands. One among them was to be nominated as Sarpanch by the Wazir-i-Wazarat (deputy commissioner). The Act was limited in its scope to empower the people at the gross root level and elitist in nature and was less in democratic character. The Act prescribed restrictive qualifications like minimum matriculate, paying at least Rs 5/- as revenue tax and annual income of at least 700 and property worth Rs 1000 etc. for voters as well as for contesting candidates. Only three per cent of people could vote and stand for election. So the system was in no sense close to empower the citizens but was rather to use panchayats as an extended arm of the Government for judicial and civil administration.

In 1941, the 1935 Act was amended to

cover wide range of subjects including civic and development functions. The Panchayats were empowered to maintain public roadways, moveable and immovable public properties, and other constructions in the villages. They were also given the authority to levy taxes and generate resources for the village's growth, as well as to build and maintain public roads, bridges, wells, ponds, and water reservoirs. The Panchayat was also given jurisdiction over the locations of slaughterhouses, as well as the examination and inspection of weights and measures.

Many new developments occurred in the State following 1947. In March 1948, the National Conference was elected to power. The state's development scenario at the time was marked by economic stagnation and educational adversity. Through deception, the Jagirdars and Chakdars had amassed vast of land. The majority of the population was poor. In light of this, the government made the eradication of landlordism a primary priority. It led to the introduction of the Big Landed Estates Abolition Act of 1950. This was a watershed moment in J&K's history because it was the subcontinent's first land reform initiative.

In line with the long commitment of the party towards democratic decentralization, Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah headed government passed the Jammu and Kashmir Village Panchayat Act 1951, providing for the establishment of village panchayats on democratic principles and repealed the Village Panchayat Regulation of 1935 and 1941. The Act provided for majority of the Panchayat members to be elected on the basis of adult franchise; introduction of concept of Halqa Panchayats comprising 5-7 villages; Introduction of Panchayat board at each Tehsil; and Identification of sources of revenue for panchayats. The Act assigned the panchayats administration, development, civic and judicial functions.

By 1941, the state had established 540 panchayats, which were engaged in dehat sudhar (village improvement) activities such as road repair, irrigation canal deepening and widening, ration distribution, and the resolution of local disputes such as land disputes, theft, family feuds, and inter-village disputes. It's worth noting

that Panchayat raj was created as part of a democratic reform movement to eliminate the oppressive and exploitative social structures left over from the Dogra era in communities and connect them to a new dawn.

This reform movement, however, was derailed after Sheikh Abdullah's government was removed from the office and he was imprisoned in August 1953. Following the Indira-Abdullah Accord in 1975, Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah's government implemented a number of administrative reforms regarding decentralisation; he introduced an innovative developmental strategy "the Single Line Administration (SLA) Model" to secure the participation of people through their representatives in the development process. Planning and decision-making authority over a certain plan size was decentralised from state capitals to district level under the SLA. However, over time, the institutional framework of the District Development Boards has been eroded, and it has become "Multi-Line," and its autonomy has been jeopardised, compromising its efficacy.

The need to have a good institutional framework to provide the community a distinct and positive role in matters of self-governance has created a sense of urgency for redesigning the Panchayati Raj institutional structure. The Jammu and Kashmir Panchayati Raj Act, 1989, was enacted as a result of this realisation.

Since 1935, for the first time an Act was named as the "Panchayati Raj Act, rather than a "Village Panchayat Regulation Act". The former implies the promotion of three tier Panchayati raj (at village, block, and district levels) in the state; in contrast the latter was confined to the promotion of one tier Panchayat raj at village level under (1935 & 1941 Panchayat Acts) and then two-tier Panchayati raj at village and at Block level under (1951 & 1958 Panchayat Acts). It also provides Panchayat Adalat (Panchayat Court) for each Halqa Panchayat to settle petty local disputes.

The Panchayati Raj Act of 1989 was a significant step toward reviving dormant panchayats and institutionalising local governance, as envisioned by the leaders in the

1944 Naya Kashmir Manifesto. However, due to the rise of insurgency in the state, which brought democracy to a halt, the Act remained inactive.

Though the attempts were made to hold Panchayat elections in 2001, but the effort failed since the elections turned out to be a 'paper exercise.' Half of the Panch and Sarpanch seats in Kashmir remained unfilled due to the militants' and Hurriyat Conference's call for an electoral boycott. Instead of holding new elections as required by the J&K Panchayati Raj Act, panchayats formed in 2001 were dissolved in 2006 and the then PDP-Congress Coalition government transferred powers to the Panchayat secretary (village level worker), who was instructed to draw local plans through the convening of Gram Sabha.

After a 33-year wait, the state held its first real Panchayat elections in 2011, with 77.79 per cent of eligible voters casting ballots. In total, 33,000 Halqa (village) Panchayat representatives were elected to 4128 Halqa panchayats. The true problem, however, was transforming these organisations into effective democratic institutions and involving people in the planning and decision-making processes so that they could participate in actual governance. However, even after a great opportunity provided by high voter turnout, government failed to establish a three tier system. The Panchayati Raj institutions formed in 2011 completed its tenure in 2016 and were subsequently dissolved. Due to the civil protests and freedom marches from every nook and corner of Kashmir in 2016, the elections were delayed till 2018. In 2018, elections were held in 9 phases from 17 November to 11 December. Most areas of the valley boycotted the election, voter turn out remained low, number of the seats remained unfilled and number of candidates in the valley won un-opposed.

Among the rising heat over Article 370 revocations in valley, the parliament of India in October 2020 amended the Jammu and Kashmir Panchayati Raj Act, 1989, to hold direct elections to District Development Council (DDC) with a stated goal of strengthening democracy at the gross root level. Almost after the fourteen months of revocation of special status of Jammu

and Kashmir, the election was first political engagement which attracted the attention of the whole country. But the successful conduct of the DDC elections was highlight of 2020.

The Structure of the District Development Councils and functions :-

In October, 2020, J&K amended the J&K Panchayati Raj Act, 1989 to create a new tier of 'grassroots governance', the District Development Council (DDC). Every district in J&K will have a District Development Council having jurisdiction over the entire district, excluding municipal areas. Every DDC will have 14 directly-elected members irrespective of its area or size of population for speedy development and economic uplift. The elected members then elect the chairperson and vice-chairperson of the DDC, who are mandated to administer the district. Every DDC shall comprise directly-elected members, the chairpersons of all Block Development Councils and members of the legislative assembly from the district. However, only the 14 elected members have the power to elect or remove the chairperson and vice chairperson. The DDC supervises and implement schemes in the welfare and development sectors such as health, education and public works. It would function as a working group for formulation of periodic and annual plans for the district; and formulate and finalise the plan and non-plan budget for the district. Five standing committees, one each for finance, development, public works, health and education, and welfare will now be constituted in every DDC. The term of the DDC will be five years, and the electoral process will allow for reservations for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and women. The Additional District Development Commissioner (or the Additional DC) of the district shall be the Chief Executive Officer of the District Development Council. The council, as stated in the Act, will hold at least four "general meetings" in a year, one in each quarter. The DDC replaced the District Development Board (DDB) of the erstwhile state of J&K, in which a cabinet minister or a minister of state would chair DDBs, and members included MLAs, MLCs and MPs. In DDBs, the planning and execution of development

works was mostly done by the district development commissioners, which would not be done by the elected representatives. The elections for DDC were held in eight phases to 20 District Development Councils from November 28 to December 19 across 280 constituencies, in the first major electoral exercise since the abrogation of Article 370.

Objectives of Creating the District Development Councils and the response of public :- The J&K administration in a statement said that the move to have an elected third tier of the Panchayati Raj institution marks the implementation of the entire 73rd Amendment Act in J&K. The idea is that systems that had been made defunct by earlier J&K governments such as the Panchayati raj system are being revived under the Centre's rule in the state through the Lieutenant Governor's administration. In the absence of elected representatives in the UT, senior government officials argue that DDCs will effectively become representative bodies for development at the grass-root level in the 20 districts of the UT. They hope that this may draw some former legislators in as well.

However many people consider this an attempt to replace and disempower the indigenous politics of Kashmir. They argue that "empowering grassroots cannot be at the cost of disenfranchising locals from legislating for themselves" The PDP has said that the Centre wants Panchayat and block development, but does not want to give the people of J&K the right to frame their own laws. The party has also stated that there are "larger insecurities and concerns" such as those of demographic change that are not addressed by "such tokenism of democratic process". Senior PDP leader Naeem Akhtar in an interview with Indian Express has said the move would spell the end of politics in Jammu and Kashmir. "The aim is total de-politicisation so that there is no central collective voice. It is to cut to size the people of Jammu and Kashmir so that they don't have a political voice. The aim is to sub-divide, overlap, create layer after layer, so that nobody would know who is in charge. In such a scenario, the ultimate arbiter would be the

bureaucrats and the security set-up," Akhtar said.

Other political parties, while not being opposed to greater involvement of local representatives, have questioned the need to set up such a structure in the absence of representatives to the state Assembly. A senior member of the National Conference said the decision would have far-reaching consequences, especially in reducing the role of MLAs.

In Kashmir, it is also widely assumed that the Union government ordered the DDC elections for two reasons. The first was to mitigate the impact of Article 370's revocation of special status to the greatest degree possible. The second goal was to weaken the grip of the big political players by directing attention to more grassroots levels, allowing new players to enter the political arena. It planned to create 20 different groupings of actors, thereby diminishing the hold of the long-time key players, in order to steer the discourse by putting the districts into focus.

Formation of PAGD :- The People's Alliance for Gupkar Declaration (PAGD) is a consortium of mainstream political parties, which have been seeking the restoration of the special status of Jammu and Kashmir, which was revoked by the Narendra Modi-led Centre back in 2019. The parties include the National Conference, Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), Jammu and Kashmir Awami National Conference, Jammu and Kashmir People's Movement and the Communist Party of India. The PAGD fought the polls under a unified banner. Initially the Congress was also part of the PAGD, but later distanced from it.

Understanding the DDC election results in Jammu and Kashmir :- The first-ever District Development Council (DDC) elections in the Union territory of Jammu and Kashmir have sprung several surprises. Except for a couple of outcomes which were on expected lines, the others have been unprecedented.

The fact PAGD emerged victorious on the majority of the seats in the Kashmir valley while BJP performed well in the Jammu region as

was much expected. While the BJP is celebrating the fact that it is the single largest party with 75 wins, the PAGD has finished as the largest pre-poll alliance with 110 wins. Independents have won 50. On the other hand BJP-ally Apni Party has won 12 seats. The congress which used to be major political force in the state won only 26 seats, is behind the BJP in terms of strike rates. The BJP was ahead of the NC-PDP even in terms of the vote share in contested seats. While its contested vote share is marginally higher than the NC's, it is significantly higher than that of the PDP. This picture changes when one looks at the Kashmir and Jammu divisions separately. While all the 10 districts of the Kashmir Valley are dominated by the Muslims, six of the ten districts in Jammu are dominated by the Hindu districts. The remaining four districts of Rajouri, Ponch, Doda and Kashtiwari which border the Kashmir valley have sizeable Muslim population.

The DDC poll results have once again highlighted the communal polarisation in Jammu and Kashmir. The BJP has won 86% of the 56 seats in the entirely Hindu districts while it has won only 2% of the 152 seats in the entirely Muslim districts. The PAGD has won 57% seats in the entirely Muslim districts compared to just 4% in the entirely Hindu districts.

However a vote-share comparison with the 2014 assembly and 2019 Lok Sabha elections shows that the BJP continues to be an insignificant player in the Kashmir region. Because local body elections are fought in a very different manner compared to national or even state elections.

Overall, the DDC elections have only succeeded in mirroring Jammu and Kashmir's decade-old fault lines. The BJP was unable to make deeper inroads into Kashmir, while the PAGD-combine was unable to establish any hegemony in the Jammu region.

Thus, if the Union government's goal was to draw attention away from the big actors at the subnational level by creating a new tier at the district level, the degree of success achieved is yet to be evaluated.

Voter turnout has been an important factor in every election in Jammu and Kashmir.

After militancy which erupted in the late 1980s, voter participation in the former state, notably in the Kashmir area, dropped. Kashmir's voter turnout in the 2019 Lok Sabha elections was the lowest in two decades. The DDC elections showed a 51 per cent voter turnout in the Union territory, but this was skewed towards the Jammu region. In the Jammu regions, almost 68 per cent of registered voters voted, whereas just 34% voted in the Kashmir region.

Conclusion :- That Jammu and Kashmir's politics polarised around its religious geography is well known. The DDC elections have only succeeded in mirroring Jammu and Kashmir's decade-old fault lines. The BJP was unable to make deeper inroads into Kashmir, while the PAGD-combine was unable to establish any hegemony in the Jammu region. The DDC poll results have once again highlighted the communal polarisation in Jammu and Kashmir. The BJP has won 86% of the 56 seats in the entirely Hindu districts while it has won only 2% of the 152 seats in the entirely Muslim districts. The PAGD has won 57% seats in the entirely Muslim districts compared to just 4% in the entirely Hindu districts. Voter turnout has been an important factor in every election in Jammu and Kashmir. After militancy which erupted in the late 1980s, voter participation in the former state, notably in the Kashmir area, dropped. Kashmir's voter turnout in the 2019 Lok Sabha elections was the lowest in two decades. The DDC elections this year showed a 51 per cent voter turnout in the Union territory, but this was skewed towards the Jammu region. Furthermore the formation of the DDC is seen by many in Kashmir as undermining actual democracy in the region, whilst the Union government believes it will promote democracy at the grassroots level and fulfil a constitutional need under the 73rd Amendment. The direct election process has been criticised for not adhering to democratic principles because there is no proportional representation because each district has 14 seats that are not apportioned based on population.

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